

Consiglio Nazionale
delle Ricerche

NextGenIT
Consolidation of the Italian Infrastructure
for Omics Data and Bioinformatics

ELIXIR-IT All Hands Meeting 2023

**"Bringing together
Communities and Platforms"**

November 27th-28th

📍 CNR - Rome, Italy

Compute Platform

Giacinto Donvito

INFN

Outlook

- Platform status
- Upgrade on public funded projects
- Services and capabilities
- Contact points

(Main) Platform sites

CNR - Area
della Ricerca
Milano 4

CINECA

ReCaS
INFN Bari - UniBA

CNR - Area
della Ricerca
Napoli 1

CNR - ReCaS

Service for Data Replication

BioRepository

LARGE-ARCHIVE AND
DATAPROTECTION REPOSITORY

- High-performance parallel storage solution
- Parallel file system
- Ports: 10/40/100GbE

- **3x5 PB storage**
Bari, Naples, Milan

Can provide geographic
replica of critical data

Status Cloud Services

- ReCaS-INFN/UNIBA (New OpenStack-based infrastructure)
 - 3000 Cpu/Cores
 - 24TB of RAM
 - 3 Pbyte of cloud storage
- CNR-ITB (@ReCaS)
 - 10'000 Cpu/Cores
 - 40TB of RAM
 - 2 Pbyte of Cloud Storage

Status HPC/HTC Services

- ReCaS-INFN/UNIBA (HTCondor//Docker orchestrator)

24000 Cpu/Cores

10 Pbyte of cloud storage

20 Pbyte of Tape storage

20 NVIDIA GPU (V100/A100)

- CINECA

Marconi/Galileo100 Super Computing clusters

about 6 Mhours (last year) allocated

<https://www.hpc.cineca.it/systems/hardware/galileo100/>

GARR contribution to Elixir-IT

- Network: in its role as the National Research and Education Network, GARR provides support for any connectivity issue within Italy and between Italy and abroad.
- Computing: GARR operates an OpenStack-based cloud and a Kubernetes-based container platform.
 - Both of them are open to researchers belonging to institutions connected by GARR, as well as all participants to projects/activities in which GARR is involved.
- Identity and applications: Pietro Mandreoli (GARR fellowship) is configuring an instance of Laniakea on GARR cloud, and adding support for IAM Identity Provider.
- Training: talks are ongoing with GARR training team. Several possible forms of collaboration are envisaged (co-locate event, co-host material, provide technical support,...).

Elixir-IT Compute Platform - CRS4

- CRS4 offers more than 400 compute nodes divided in different clusters
 - a total more than 5500 computational cores available
 - Several fat nodes (256 GB - 1 TB RAM)
- Most clusters interconnected with Infiniband or 10 GbE
- Over **two** petabytes of storage
- Connected to the GARR at 1 Gbps
- Support for containerized workloads on HPC cluster
- Expertise focused on **DNA and RNA sequencing applications**
- Support and expertise for **Galaxy workflows** and **Big Data analytics workloads**
 - E.g., Hadoop and Flink

ENEA contribution to Elixir-IT

<http://www.ict.enea.it>
<http://www.cresco.enea.it>

- 1. ENEA is the Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development.** ENEA operates in a range of R&D sectors, including energy technologies, new materials, life and environmental sciences. In support of the institutional research activities.
- 2. The ENEA IT division** provides computing and storage resources, integrated into ENEAGRID, a computational infrastructure distributed over six geographical sites in Italy. The computing core of ENEAGRID is represented by the HPC CRESCO clusters.
- 3. In May 2018, CRESCO6** was inaugurated at ENEA Portici. CRESCO6 is a 1.4Pflop/s machine. It ranked 420th in the **TOP500 list of Nov. 2018**. CRESCO6 succeeded CRESCO4 and CRESCO5, two older HPC clusters already installed in the same data center (they are still in service), with a nominal computing power of 0.1 and 0.025 Pflop/s respectively.

ENEA contribution to Elixir-IT

CRESCO6 has 434 nodes for a total of **20832 cores**.

It is based on Lenovo ThinkSystem SD530 platform, a two-socket server in a 0.5 U rack form factor inserted in a 2U four-mode enclosure.

Each node is equipped with:

- 2 Intel Xeon Platinum 8160 CPUs, each with 24 cores with a clock frequency of 2.1 GHz
- RAM of 192 GB, corresponding to 4 GB/core
- Nodes are interconnected by an Intel Omni-Path network with 21 Intel Edge switches 100 series of 48 ports each, bandwidth equal to 100 GB/s, latency equal to 100ns. The connections between the nodes have 2 tier 2:1 nonblocking tapered fat-tree topology. The consumption of electrical power during massive computing workloads is 190 kW.

Computing platforms

Cluster name (Linux x86_64)	Network	Cores/Tflops
CRESCO6 INTEL/SKL	OPA	20832/~1400
CRESCO4 INTEL/SNB	IB QDR	4944/~100
CRESCO5 INTEL/HAS	IB QDR	640/~25
K40/PHI/Large RAM	IB QDR	300/~17
Total		~26716/~1500

Storage

Storage Systems	Bandwidth GB/s	network	Capacity
1 x DDN S2A9900	4	IB QDR	0.6 PB
2 x DDN SFA7700	15	IB QDR	1 PB
2 x Dot-Hill 3730	8	FC/8Gbps	0.5 PB
3 x RAID Servers	1.25	10 GEth	72 TB
1 x Dot-Hill 3000	1.25	FC/8Gbps	12 TB
1 x DS 4700	0.8	FC/4bps	26 TB
Total			~2.2 PB
1 x DDN SFA7790	20	EDR	1 PB

Applications services for ELIXIR:

- Access to parallel computing nodes
- Large data repositories
- Machine learning tools
- Molecular modeling codes

ELIXIR HPC@CINECA – State of the art

HPC-resources

Training

Challenging use-cases

<https://www.hpc.cineca.it/systems/hardware/leonardo/>

ELIXIR HPC@CINECA calls – State of the art

- 123 received proposals;
- 93% acceptance rate;
- 130 TB permanent storage
- 6 Millions core-hours allocated

Research Topics

Affiliation Count

How to get access - “ELIXIR HPC@CINECA”

The **ELIXIR-IT HPC@CINECA Call** offers computational resources to researchers from ELIXIR-ITA, other ELIXIR Nodes and any European research institution ([Tiny URL](#) to access to the form, projects are evaluated with a “first come, first served” policy.)

- **50k** core hours
- **1TB** permanent \$WORK for data **storage**
- **12 months**
- Specialist support (e.g. HPC speedup; automation strategies; workflow management systems)
- Environment configuration

Default values of the provided resources when a project is created on the cluster. They can be rimodulated upon needs if properly motivated

Castrignano et al. BMC Bioinformatics 2020, 21(Suppl 1):352
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12859-020-03565-8>

BMC Bioinformatics

SOFTWARE

Open Access

ELIXIR-IT HPC@CINECA: high performance computing resources for the bioinformatics community

Tiziana Castrignano^{1*}, Silvia Giolosa^{2,3}, Tiziano Flati^{2,3}, Mirko Cestari², Ernesto Picardi^{3,4}, Matteo Chiara^{3,5}, Maddalena Fratelli⁶, Stefano Amente⁷, Marco Cirilli⁸, Marco Antonio Tangaro⁹, Giovanni Chillemi^{3,9}, Graziano Pesole^{1,4*} and Federico Zambelli^{3,5*}

From 13th Bioinformatics and Computational Biology Conference - BBCC 2018
Naples, Italy, 19-21 November 2018

CINECA

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32838759/>

Training

- Cineca is involved in the **teaching team** and provides a **Virtual Machine** on the ADA-cloud reserved to **tutors and students** for the entire duration of the course and.

The **environment is pre-configured** with the most commonly used tools in Bioinformatics (conda environments, R packages, Python, scientific libraries, read aligners and so on)

- Students have their own working areas where they can **learn to code and store and analyze** the data to prepare the course final elaborations.

Use-cases: useGalaxy public servers

CINECA • ELIXS_EuSciGat mtangaro

Project / Compute / Instances

Instances

Instance ID: Filter [Launch Instance](#) [Delete Instances](#) [More Actions](#)

Displaying 13 items

<input type="checkbox"/>	Instance Name	Image Name	IP Address	Flavor	Key Pair	Status	Availability Zone	Task	Power State	Age	Actions
<input type="checkbox"/>	usegalaxy.backup	Rocky-9-GenericCloud.I atest.x86_64.qcow2-DB_test	192.168.0.14	fl.ada.s	cloud	Active	nova	None	Running	3 weeks, 5 days	Create Snapshot
<input type="checkbox"/>	usegalaxy.replica	Rocky-9-GenericCloud.I atest.x86_64.qcow2-DB_test	192.168.0.204	fl.ada.s	cloud	Active	nova	None	Running	3 weeks, 5 days	Create Snapshot
<input type="checkbox"/>	jenkins-bridge-wn	Ubuntu Server 20.04 LTS (Focal Fossa)	192.168.0.248, 131.175.205.30	fl.ada.xs	mtangaro-key	Active	nova	None	Running	4 weeks, 1 day	Create Snapshot
<input type="checkbox"/>	it02-exec-node-0-usegalaxy.eu	vgpp-v60-j225-1a1df01 ec8f3-dev	192.168.0.252	fl.ada.m	it02-pulsar-key	Active	nova	None	Running	1 month	Create Snapshot
<input type="checkbox"/>	it02-central-manager-usegalaxy.eu	vgpp-v60-j225-1a1df01 ec8f3-dev	192.168.0.152, 131.175.205.137	fl.ada.xs	it02-pulsar-key	Active	nova	None	Running	1 month	Create Snapshot
<input type="checkbox"/>	it02-nfs-usegalaxy.eu	vgpp-v60-j225-1a1df01 ec8f3-dev	192.168.0.189	fl.ada.xs	it02-pulsar-key	Active	nova	None	Running	1 month	Create Snapshot
<input type="checkbox"/>	usegalaxy.it-exec-test	vgpp-v60-j225-1a1df01 ec8f3-dev	192.168.0.87	fl.ada.l	cloud	Active	nova	None	Running	1 month, 2 weeks	Create Snapshot
<input type="checkbox"/>	usegalaxy.condor-nfs	vgpp-v60-j225-1a1df01 ec8f3-dev	192.168.0.249	fl.ada.m	cloud	Active	nova	None	Running	2 months, 3 weeks	Create Snapshot
<input type="checkbox"/>	usegalaxy.galaxy	Rocky-9-GenericCloud.I atest.x86_64	192.168.0.169, 131.175.207.122	fl.ada.l	cloud	Active	nova	None	Running	2 months, 3 weeks	Create Snapshot
<input type="checkbox"/>	usegalaxy.rabbitmq	Rocky-9-GenericCloud.I atest.x86_64	192.168.0.124, 131.175.207.49	fl.ada.s	cloud	Active	nova	None	Running	2 months, 3 weeks	Create Snapshot
<input type="checkbox"/>	usegalaxy.condor-central-manager	vgpp-v60-j225-1a1df01 ec8f3-dev	192.168.0.98, 131.175.207.129	fl.ada.s	cloud	Active	nova	None	Running	2 months, 3 weeks	Create Snapshot
<input type="checkbox"/>	usegalaxy.database	Rocky-9-GenericCloud.I atest.x86_64	192.168.0.90	fl.ada.l	cloud	Active	nova	None	Running	2 months, 3 weeks	Create Snapshot
<input type="checkbox"/>	master	Ubuntu Server 22.04 LTS (Jammy Jellyfish)	192.168.0.238, 131.175.207.218	fl.ada.xs	mtangaro-key	Active	nova	None	Running	3 months	Create Snapshot

Displaying 13 items

The Pulsar Network is wide job execution system distributed across several European datacenters, allowing to scale Galaxy instances computing power over heterogeneous resources, such as CINECA

INFN for Elixir-IT

INFN & ReCaS-Bari Services

- HTC/HPC
- Standard Batch System // HPC
- + GPUs
- Cloud Computing
- IaaS // PaaS // SaaS
- Cloud Storage
- S3 // Dropbox-like
- Archive Storage
- Tape system

ReCaS
Next Upgrade

- Galaxy cluster on-demand
- RStudio on-demand
- Jupyterhub on-demand
- ShareLaTeX on-demand
- Dropbox-like service based on ownCloud
- Desktop as a Service
- Moodle on-demand
- WordPress on-demand
- GitLab
- Mesos / Marathon / Chronos

ShareLaTeX

PON R&I
2014-2020
Avviso
424/2018
Azione II. 1

INFN for Elixir-IT @ReCaS-Bari

The INFN Cloud Dashboard displays a grid of service tiles. The top navigation bar includes 'INFN Cloud Dashboard', 'Deployments', 'Advanced', and a user profile for 'Marica Antonacci'. A search bar is located below the navigation. The main content area features several service tiles:

- Virtual machine
- Docker-compose
- Run docker
- Elasticsearch and Kibana
- Apache Mesos cluster
- Kubernetes cluster
- Spark + Jupyter cluster
- Data processing Cluster - HTCondor+CVMFS+NFS
- WLCG compliant site for CMS
- RStudio
- TensorFlow with Jupyter

The RECaS BARI login page is titled 'Welcome to lanikea'. It features a sign-in form with fields for 'Username' and 'Password', and a 'Sign in' button. Below the form, there is a link for 'Forgot your password?' and a section for 'Or sign in with' which includes a 'Google' button and a 'LOGIN' button. A red circle highlights the 'LOGIN' button. At the bottom, there is a 'Register a new account' button.

The Lanikea Dashboard shows a 'Most used' section with two tiles: 'Galaxy Express' and 'Galaxy Docker'. Below this is an 'All applications' section with a search bar and a grid of application tiles:

- Galaxy elastic cluster (BETA) - Live build
- Galaxy - Docker
- Galaxy cluster - Live build
- Galaxy cluster - Express
- Galaxy - Live build
- Galaxy - Express

At ReCaS-Bari there are already several services **ready-to-be-used** easy to consume

INFN for Elixir-IT @ReCaS-Bari

Galaxy

Description: Deploy Galaxy on a single Virtual Machine from a VM image (FAST). The basic configuration includes CentOS 7, the selected Galaxy flavour, companion software and reference data. Configure, click on the "Submit" button, wait for the confirmation e-mail(s) and log in to your new Galaxy instance. If after some hours you do not receive any e-mail please be sure to check your SPAM BOX.

Instance description

Virtual hardware Galaxy Advanced

Galaxy version
Galaxy release 19.05
Galaxy release 19.05 recommended

Instance description
ELIXIR-ITALY

Set Galaxy Brand

Galaxy administrator e-mail
ma.tangaro@gmail.com
Type a valid e-mail address.

Galaxy flavours
Galaxy minimal

Load Galaxy tools preset

Reference data repository
usegalaxy.org Galaxy reference data CVMFS repository
Select reference data repository

Submit Cancel

Galaxy

Description: Deploy Galaxy on a single Virtual Machine from a VM image (FAST). The basic configuration includes CentOS 7, the selected Galaxy flavour, companion software and reference data. Configure, click on the "Submit" button, wait for the confirmation e-mail(s) and log in to your new Galaxy instance. If after some hours you do not receive any e-mail please be sure to check your SPAM BOX.

Instance description

Virtual hardware Galaxy Advanced

Instance flavour
Large (4 cpu, 8 GB RAM, 20 GB disk)
CPUs, memory size (RAM), root disk size

Galaxy instance SSH public key

Leave blank this field to load your default SSH public key
Paste here your SSH public key or configure a default key

Enable encryption
Off

Encrypt instance external storage

Storage volume size
50 GB
Select storage size

Submit Cancel

- ### Tools
- search tools
- Get Data
 - Send Data
 - Collection Operations
 - Lift-Over
 - Text Manipulation
 - Convert Formats
 - Filter and Sort
 - Join, Subtract and Group
 - Fetch Alignments/Sequences
 - Operate on Genomic Intervals
 - Statistics
 - Graph/Display Data
 - Phenotype Association
 - Mapping
 - Quality Control
 - deepTools
 - BED Tools
 - SAM Tools
 - RNA-Seq
 - RNA Structure Analysis
 - RNA Alignment

Hello, Galaxy is running!

To customize this page edit [static/welcome.html](#)

- Configuring Galaxy »
- Installing Tools »

Take an interactive tour: [Galaxy UI](#) [History](#) [Scratchbook](#)

Galaxy is an open platform for supporting data intensive research. Galaxy is developed by The Galaxy Team with the support of many contributors.

The Galaxy Project is supported in part by NHGRI, NSF, The Huck Institutes of the Life Sciences, The Institute for CyberScience at Penn State, and Johns Hopkins University.

History

search datasets

Unnamed history

(empty)

This history is empty. You can load your own data or get data from an external source

Full GDPR compliance also supporting analysis on clinical data

INFN for Elixir-IT @ReCaS-Bari

INFN Cloud Dashboard Deployments Advanced

Marica Antonacci

Spark + Jupyter cluster

Description: Deploy a complete Spark+Jupyter computing cluster

Input Values **Advanced**

number_of_masters

1

num_cpus_master

4

mem_size_master

8 GB

number_of_slaves

1

num_cpus_slave

4

mem_size_slave

8 GB

Submit

Cancel

[Apache Spark](#) is a must for Big data's lovers. In a few words, Spark is a fast and powerful framework that provides an API to perform massive distributed processing over resilient sets of data.

[Jupyter Notebook](#) is a popular application that enables you to edit, run and share Python code into a web view. It allows you to modify and re-execute parts of your code in a very flexible way. That's why Jupyter is a great tool to test and prototype programs.

Jupyter Untitled Last Checkpoint: a minute ago (unsaved changes)

Logout

File Edit View Insert Cell Kernel Widgets Help

Trusted Python 2

```
In [1]: from __future__ import absolute_import, division, print_function, unicode_literals

try:
    # %tensorflow_version only exists in Colab.
    %tensorflow_version 2.x
except Exception:
    pass
import tensorflow as tf
print("Num GPUs Available: ", len(tf.config.experimental.list_physical_devices('GPU')))

Num GPUs Available: 1
```

In []:

Laniakea and the ReCaS-Bari service

Galaxy
community talk
tomorrow

LANIAKEA is a cloud based Galaxy instance provider: users can deploy Galaxy instances over Cloud resources:

- No need for the end user to know the underlying infrastructure.
- No need for maintenance of the hardware and software infrastructure.

Laniakea@ReCaS: ELIXIR-ITALY and ReCaS-Bari datacenter provide the possibility to exploits Laniakea for deploying Galaxy virtual environments

Laniakea architecture (simplified view)

Laniakea aims to solve the problems of the other options for using Galaxy and other services.

It provides:

- Proper hardware resources
- Private and customizable Galaxy instances
- Storage encryption for sensitive data analysis

Laniakea@ReCaS resource availability

Current Laniakea@ReCas version is limited on deploying only Galaxy.

Next version, expected by the end of 2023, will feature the deployment of other applications, like RStudio, Jupyter and IRIDA.

Service	Laniakea@ReCaS (current)	Laniakea@ReCaS (Next)
PaaS requirements	10 vCPUs 20 GB RAM	10 vCPUs 20 GB RAM
Users vCPUs	250 vCPUs	500 vCPUs
Users RAM (GB)	500 GB RAM	1 TB RAM
Users Storage	10 TB	250 TB
Jenkins	1 CM and 2 WN (all cloud) shared with usegalaxy-it	1 CM and 2 WN (all cloud) shared with usegalaxy-it
CVMFS	Already data.galaxyproject.org mirror at GARR.	Already data.galaxyproject.org mirror at GARR.

PNRR investments

- National Centres
 - CN1
 - CN3
- Research infrastructures
 - TERABIT
 - ElixirXNextGenIT

PNRR investments: CN1

- Upgrade to HTC/HPC and Cloud resources at **INFN@ReCaS**
Mostly CPU, Storage and working on a ISO27001 Certification for the cloud environment
- Upgrade to HPC and Cloud resources at **CINECA**
Mostly CPU, Storage and GPU (LEONARDO HPC cluster: 2° in the TOP500 in EU, 6° Worldwide)

PNRR investments: CN3

- Upgrade to HTC/HPC and Cloud **UNIBA@ReCaS** resources
Mostly CPU, Storage, GPU

RNA
& GENETHERAPY

PNRR investments: ElixirXNextGenIT

- Upgrade to HTC/HPC and Cloud **UNIBA@ReCaS** resources
Mostly upgrading CPU, Storage, GPU, Tape storage
- Upgrade to Computing and Storage Resources at **UNIMI**
Mostly upgrading existing INDACO infrastructure
- Upgrade HPC cluster and data storage at **UNIPD**
- Dedicated infrastructure for computing (CPU and GPU bases) and data storage at **UNIBO**

Conclusions

- Synergies among large number of projects and funds assure that the activities of the ICT partners, are able to continue fulfilling Elixir-IT requirements over a quite long period of time
- PNRR is building on an already solid and reliable distributed infrastructure made of high-level services for data analytics and management
- Collaborating with Elixir-IT (and Elixir at large: we are well in-line with IP/CS of Elixir-Hub activities) is challenging and scientifically interesting for us (as technological partner) to improve and better develop our computing technologies
- The know-how of the “technological partners” is the key added value for the Elixir-IT partners exploiting not only “ICT services” (and resources), but mainly working together to implement co-developed “community services”.

